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DEVELOPMENT OF LITERARY EDUCATION COMPETENCIES OF HEARING IMPAIRED CHILDREN

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11468715>

Abstract: This thesis describes the study and solution of ways, methods, means and problems of developing literary competence in students with hearing impairment.

Key words: Album, analyzer, questionnaire, application, knowledge, material, communication, lesson, program, notebook, writing, hard of hearing, correction.

Introduction:

In our country, it is planned to improve the measures related to the state support of the disabled, their full education, and their integration into the society along with healthy people. Important tasks such as "...to strengthen the social protection of the needy segments of the population and state support for the elderly and disabled persons". By developing oral speech as a communication tool of hearing-impaired persons, they are spiritually mature, harmonious and well-developed in all aspects, independent thinkers, have intellectual potential, deep knowledge and a modern worldview, suitable for the fate and future of our country. It is important to bring up the young generation capable of taking responsibility.

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The educational system is the main foundation of the country's development, and it requires the systematic organization of pedagogical activities based on detailed and clear plans. It is possible to mention the large-scale work carried out in this field, in particular, our adopted nationwide programs on education. loyalty to values, pride in the rich spiritual heritage of

our great ancestors and educating them in the spirit of further enrichment" requires improvement of methodical works.

Recently, effective approaches have been introduced in our country to update the content of education in accordance with the requirements of international educational standards. In particular, state educational standards, curricula and training programs based on the competency approach, as well as new generation textbooks, are being created, and serious attention is being paid to the development of students' abilities, learning and abilities. Therefore, educating an independent-minded person who can do a decent job in any situation, who has a firm and firm position in his beliefs, in a word, a competent person is the main criterion for the development of society.

The word competence ("sompotence" comes from the word "tocompete") means "to compete", "to compete", "to compete". Literally translated, it means "ability to compete". It is noted in psychological and pedagogical sources that competence is considered to be a very complex, multi-part concept, which is common to many disciplines. Therefore, its interpretations are different in terms of volume, content, meaning, and logical content. The essence of the term is that it is characterized by concepts such as "efficiency", "adaptability", "achievement", "readability", "success", "effectiveness", "comprehensibility", "property", "quality", "quantity".

In research on competence and its classification, this concept is used to show the final results of education and to describe various characteristics of a person. The main function of competencies in education is the manifestation of social demand in preparing the young generation for life; show real objects in the environment for purposeful application of knowledge, skills, skills and methods of activity in a complex manner; in addition to being a component of the content of various educational tools and educational fields, it consists in being able to apply theoretical knowledge in practice in solving such problems. The history of the introduction of the concept of competence into science and life is as follows:

In the first stage (1960s-1970s), the initial competence in language learning was included, and it was carried out by the concept of "communicative competence" by Dell Hymes.

In the second stage (1970-1990s), the categories of competence and competence were used to study communication in a second (other than mother tongue) language, its theory and practice in management, leadership,

FRANCE

FRANCE

management and professionalism. Also, the content of the concept of "social competence" was developed.

The use of educational technologies in the educational process encourages students to think independently, freely, to strive, to approach all issues creatively, to feel responsibility, to analyze, to effectively use additional tools, and to be interested in their chosen profession. 'atadi. Classes organized with the help of innovative educational technologies are aimed at students to search for information, to study and analyze independently, to draw their own conclusions. The difference between lessons based on pedagogical technology and traditional lessons is that the student is given the opportunity to express his opinion independently.

A friendly learning environment is created by asking questions that do not affect the student's personality. An important part of the educational process based on pedagogical technology is to start each lesson with the creation of a set of rules based on the goal and to support the meaningful passage of the lesson. At this stage of the lesson process, it is necessary to invite students to come up with their ideas and suggestions, and at the same time to write down all ideas and suggestions regularly. The rules written as short and understandable as possible are explained by the students with the help of the teacher. In particular, the following notes are written on the board:

- do not react negatively and do not evaluate (participants do not discuss, evaluate and criticize the opinions of others);
- the answers will not be wrong (don't be afraid to make mistakes);
- change your thoughts, enrich them (make changes to students' thoughts, give additional comments, justify your thoughts);
- keep calm and participate (create an atmosphere of mutual support and fair competition).

It is necessary to remind the students about the rules and ideas in order to guide and encourage them in the educational process. Pedagogical technology is a process that develops new ways of the educational system, in which the teacher is responsible. Because its main task is to deliver information to students in a clear and understandable way. Students should receive news and be inclined to it, regardless of their character, teachers should be able to think independently, should be taught to observe and draw conclusions. In addition to the formation of knowledge, skills and abilities of students, the reforms in the educational system envisage instilling patriotic ideas into their minds and hearts. In these processes and situations, the rich spiritual heritage, traditions and

customs of our people are carried out by instilling in the heart of the student. The above goal can be realized by studying topics and analyzing sentences in the science of mother tongue. But because the sentences given in some exercises are not equally understandable for the students, the process of working on the sentences can be somewhat complicated and boring. This situation can have a negative impact on the quality of education. Therefore, education based on teacher-student cooperation should be formed. In the course of the 6th grade mother tongue education, we give as an example the formation of basic and subject-related competencies in students using the "Tanishuv" technology tool on the example of the topic "Types of Text":

The purpose of the technology:

- introducing the participants of the educational team, creating a friendly and creative environment;
- to open the creative possibilities and personal qualities of students; creating a comfortable environment for working in the classroom.

At the beginning of the lesson, the teacher divides the students into small groups. In each small group, he introduces students born in the same season of the year and gives the following task:

- describe the season you were born in (artistic-musical, scenic, humorous, etc.);
- introduce the general character of people born at this time of the year, as well as the similarities and unique aspects of group participants; describe this season;
- send creative wishes to the group participants of another season.

The teacher introduces students to the rules of presentation. Preparation time is allocated and conditions are created so that students can complete the assigned task on time. The groups begin preparation. Through the first stage of "Tanishuv" technology, the students get to know each other and have a friendly relationship.

In the second stage, the groups will present their creative performances. They comment on the texts in the exercises given in the native language textbook. They put titles on the texts and comment on each of them. First, they read and analyze the texts written on "Story text", "Illustrative text" and "Discussion text".

The first group: about the text of the story.

The second group: about descriptive text.

The third group: about the discussion text.

Group 1. The text of the story. "Iftikhar"

"Finally, we were going to fly from London to Tashkent. As soon as we boarded the aircraft, a calm and pleasant voice sounded: "Hello, ladies and gentlemen! We congratulate you on behalf of the national airline "Uzbekistan Havo Yollari!" I honestly had tears in my eyes. These words sounded in my language, in my mother tongue! Thousands of miles away from my homeland, on a ship with hundreds of foreign passengers! At least for this situation I am ready to bow a thousand times to Independence!" (Otkir Hashimov)

The participants of the first group will tell why the given text with the title "Iftikhar" is in the text of the story and its definition.

Group 2. Illustrated text. "The Island and the River"

"The island is there. If you look at it from afar, you can't get enough of it. The river, which flows like a snake, is divided into two when it comes here, and after three miles it unites again. The island in the middle of the Koshkokil river is shining. Suddenly, there was a lot of shouting and screaming as if the place had been robbed. The leaves of the tree bent over the water shine like silver. The surroundings are silent. The flow of the river and the swaying of the thick trees on the island are also magnificent" (Tahir Malik).

The participants of the second group interpret what is given and what is depicted in the pictorial text entitled "The Island and the River".

Group 3. Discussion text. "Navroz"

"Navroz is such a value of the Uzbek people that it shows the existence and greatness of the nation. Nowruz is without a doubt a holiday of living, growing and developing together with our people. Navruz, which is an integral part of the history and culture of the people, has ancient roots, but at the same time, it is renewed and re-energised every year. it also appears as a symbol"(Sh. Turdimov).

The participants of the third group explain what is discussed in the text titled "Navroz" and what the text is about.

After each performance, other group participants can complete the creative work presented and ask questions about the topic. The questions are based on the text and are as follows:

1. What is the text of the story?

Answer: In the text of the story, certain subjects or events are reported and narrated.

2. What is descriptive text?

Answer: A descriptive text is a descriptive text in which a specific object or event is described. The descriptive text is more often used in fiction.

3. What is a discussion text?

Answer: A discussion text is a text that expresses opinions about a specific subject or event. Discussion text is more commonly used in textbooks and scientific books.

Language plays an important role in forming and expressing thoughts, expressing impressions and feelings. So, people's interactions, feelings, experiences and situations are determined through language. The need for in-depth study of the mother tongue at school arises from the main functions of the language. Grades 5-6 mother tongue education expands children's thinking activity, independent thinking, understanding the opinions of others, following the culture of communication, fluently expressing one's thoughts orally and in writing, freely communicating with members of society communication serves to form skills and competencies. Implementation of these tasks largely depends on the teacher's skills. Development of students' linguistic competences in mother tongue education Approaching the student as a subject of educational activities; to ensure the creative cooperation of the teacher and the student; systematization of forms, methods, means of teaching; incorporate work on language units into each stage of the lesson project; improvement of lexical-grammatical exercises; Tasks such as continuous study of students' activities, mastery level, analysis of results, elimination of problems are of great importance.

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